

Fluoresceins and Rhodamines of the Mixed Type.

BY NARENDRA NATH GHATAK AND SIKHIBHUSHAN DUTT.

From the point of view of colour and chemical constitution, the fluoresceins and the rhodamines belong to a class of dyestuffs which offer interesting possibilities for generalisation. For example, it is possible from a study of them, to find out the influence of the position of a hydroxy or an amino group on the fluoran nucleus. It has already been pointed out by Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 107) that the nearer a hydroxy group to the pyrone oxygen atom, the greater is the development of colour. Thus in alkaline(KOH) solution :

Though, of course, a large number of pyronine dyestuffs have been prepared from various dibasic acids like succinic (Dutt and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 2524), quinolinic (Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **115**, 1102), naphthalic (Terisse, *Annalen*, 1885, **227**, 1102), diphenic (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **123**, 225), camphoric (Sircar and Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1283; and Singh, Rai and Lal, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1421); imidazole-dicarboxylic (Tewari and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 201) and many similar acids, possessing widely different colour and dyeing properties, yet in none of these series of compounds a complete generalisation has yet been attempted regarding the chemical constitution and the colour of the substance. Besides it has been found that the effect of various acid residues on the colour of these substances is not so marked as for

example in the change from gallein to hydroxyquinol-phthalein and then to phloroglucinol-phthalein. By condensing resorcinol with these dibasic acids of various characters a number of fluoresceins are obtained, all of which possess different shades of yellow or orange colour and absorption maxima between $\lambda 4900$ and $\lambda 5000$, and are characterised by the intense yellow-green fluorescence which their solutions exhibit. But in none of these cases the colour change is so marked as from blue to pink and from pink to orange.

According to a theory of colour on the basis of molecular strain which has been advanced by one of the present authors (Dutt, *loc. cit.*), whenever there is an oxygen atom in a ring system, it becomes a seat of strain on account of the distortion of its normal valency directions, and therefore in the fluoran nucleus, which is the parent nucleus of all these pyronine dyestuffs, the pyrone oxygen atom is the seat of strain which essentially determines the condition of equilibrium of the dye molecule. Hence it is evident that the nearer a hydroxy or an amino group is to the oxygen atom in a dye molecule the greater will be the colour of the substance. This can be clearly seen from the table given at the end of the paper.

Mixed fluoresceins and rhodamines, *i.e.*, phthalein dyestuffs in which the substituents in the two sides of the fluoran nucleus are dissimilar, are an interesting class of dyestuffs prepared by condensing 2:4-dihydroxy benzoyl benzoic acid with aromatic hydroxy or amino-hydroxy compounds in accordance with the diagram given below :

in which R, R₁, R₂, R₃ may be H, OH, NH₂, N(CH₃)₂, N(C₂H₅)₂, etc. These dyes are interesting in view of the fact that many of them are applicable to both metallic and tannin mordanted cotton yielding brilliant fast shades. The following aromatic hydroxy and amino-hydroxy compounds have been condensed with 2:4-dihydroxy benzoyl-benzoic acid and the corresponding phthalein obtained: phenol,

o-cresol, *m*-cresol, *p*-cresol, catechol, resorcinol, quinol, thymol, carvacrol, α -naphthol, β -naphthol, 2:7-dihydroxy-naphthalene, pyrogallol, phloroglucinol, *m*-dimethylamidophenol and *m*-diethylamidophenol. The nomenclature of these compounds has been arrived at by considering them as substituted derivatives of fluoran :

Most of these compounds are intensely fluorescent, and they dye silk, wool and mordanted cotton beautiful bright shades. For the sake of abbreviation the properties of these compounds are summarised in the form of a table given at the end of the paper.

In the case of several compounds described in this paper, such as those derived from phenol, *o*-cresol, *m*-cresol, thymol, α -naphthol and β -naphthol, the *ortho* as well as the *para* condensation is theoretically possible, but it has been found that in every case the *ortho* compound is invariably formed. This is probably due to the fact that only in the *ortho* condensation the fluoran nucleus which is very stable is capable of formation. That all the compounds described in this paper are derivatives of fluoran is shown by the fact that on distillation with zinc dust they all yield phenyl xanthene, m.p. 137°.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2:4-Dihydroxy-benzoyl-benzoic acid.—This was prepared according to the method of Baeyer (*Annalen*, 1876, 183, 23) with some modification. Sodium hydroxide (160 g.) in water (80 c.c.) was maintained at 160-165°, and fluorescein (80 g.) added with vigorous stirring. The intense violet colour which at first developed, gradually faded to a straw yellow colour and the completion of the reaction was ascertained when a small sample of the melt dissolved in water without any fluorescence. The melt on cooling was dissolved in water (400 c.c.)

and the dihydroxy benzoyl benzoic acid precipitated by hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow shining plates melting at 201° (yield, 48 gms.).

6-Hydroxy-fluoran.—The dihydroxy benzoyl benzoic acid (30 g.) was heated with crystallised phenol (12 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) for 17 hours at 140°. The excess of phenol was distilled off in steam, and the condensation product powdered, dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution, filtered and reprecipitated by dilute hydrochloric acid. It was then crystallised from dilute alcohol (yield, 16 gms.).

4:6-Dihydroxy-fluoran obtained from 2:4-dihydroxy benzoyl-benzoic acid and catechol in a manner similar to the above, crystallised from dilute acetic acid. Yield 53%.

1:6-Dihydroxy-fluoran.—The condensation product with resorcinol was separated into two compounds by means of chloroform, one of which was identified to be ordinary fluorescein, while the other was isomeric with it. From the method of formation it is quite evident that this latter compound cannot be anything else but 1:6-dihydroxy-fluoran (yield, 27%, fluorescein, 63%).

2:3-Dihydroxy-fluoran was obtained from 2:4-dihydroxy benzoyl benzoic acid and quinol in a manner similar to the catechol compound. It crystallised from alcohol (yield, 42%).

3:4:6-Trihydroxy-fluoran.—A mixture of 2:4-dihydroxy-benzoyl benzoic acid (10 g.), pyrogallol (6 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (3 c.c.) was heated at 150° for 9 hours. The condensation product was dissolved in absolute alcohol and precipitated with petroleum ether. It was finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid (yield 50%).

1:3:6-Trihydroxy-fluoran was obtained from the dihydroxy-benzoyl benzoic acid and phloroglucinol in a manner similar to the above. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid (yield, 65%).

4-Methyl-6-hydroxy-fluoran.—A mixture of the acid (3 g.), *o*-cresol (1.5 g.) and tin-tetrachloride (4 g.) was heated at 120° for 15 hours. The melt was extracted with dilute ammonia, filtered and the fluoran precipitated from the filtrate by acetic acid. It was then crystallised from dilute alcohol (yield, 70%).

3-Methyl-6-hydroxy-fluoran was prepared from *m*-cresol in a manner similar to the above. It crystallised from methyl alcohol. (Yield, 47%).

2-Methyl-6-hydroxy-fluoran was prepared from 2:4-dihydroxy-benzoyl-benzoic acid and *p*-cresol by using concentrated sulphuric acid

instead of tin-tetrachloride as condensing agent. It crystallised from dilute alcohol (yield, 53%).

1-Methyl-4-isopropyl-6-hydroxy-fluoran.—The acid (3 g.) and thymol (2 g.) were heated together at 135° for 16 hours without the use of any condensing agent. Any unchanged thymol was distilled off in steam, and the condensation product dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide, filtered and reprecipitated with acetic acid. It was then crystallised from alcohol (yield, 40%). The use of a condensing agent lowers the yield and makes the compound more difficult to purify.

1-isoPropyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-fluoran was obtained from the acid and carvacrol in a manner similar to the above with the exception that a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were used as the condensing agent. It crystallised from dilute alcohol (yield, 46%).

3:4-Phenylene-6-hydroxy-fluoran.—A mixture of the acid (3 g.), α -naphthol (2 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (3 g.) was heated at 120° for 8 hours. The product was powdered, dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide, filtered and reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from acetic acid (yield, 41%).

2:3-Phenylene-6-hydroxy-fluoran.—It was prepared from the acid and β -naphthol in a manner similar to the above. It crystallised from dilute alcohol (yield, 40%).

2:3-(4'-Hydroxy)-phenylene-6-hydroxy-fluoran was prepared from the acid and 2:7-dihydroxy-naphthalene in a manner similar to the above. It crystallised from dilute alcohol (yield 38%).

3-Dimethylamido-6-hydroxy-fluoran.—A mixture of the acid (10 g.), *m*-dimethylamido-phenol (6 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (1.5 g.) was heated at 125° for 10 hours. The product was powdered and extracted with alcohol. The alcoholic extract on dilution with water gave a precipitate of the fluoran which was subsequently recrystallised from benzene (yield 43%).

3-Diethylamido-6-hydroxy-fluoran was obtained from the acid and *m*-diethylamido-phenol in a manner similar to the above. It crystallised from dilute alcohol (yield, 51%).

Properties of the fluoresceins and the rhodamines of the mixed type.

Name. (F = Fluoran).	Appearance.	M.p.	Absorption maxima (λ).	Shade on silk and wool.	Colour of solu- tion.	Colour of fluores- cence.	Analyses. (Theoretical values in brackets).
6-Hydroxy-F	... Yellow needles	181°	4980	Light yellow	Bright yellow	Yellow-green	C = 75.8(75.9); H = 4.1(3.8)%.
4 : 6-Dihydroxy-F	... Yellowish-grey needles.	179°	4950	Light brown	Brownish yellow	" "	C = 71.9(72.3); H = 3.8(3.6)%.
1 : 6-Dihydroxy-F	... Bright yellow needles.	Above 280°	4930	Brown-yellow	Orange yellow	" "	C = 72.1(72.3); H = 4.0(3.6)%.
2 : 6-Dihydroxy-F	... Yellow needles.	177°	4920	Pale yellow	Yellow	" "	C = 72.1(72.3); H = 4.0(3.6)%.
3 : 4 : 6-Trihydroxy-F	Buck-red "	189°	4950	Greyish brown	Dirty brown	C = 68.6(68.9); H = 3.5(3.4)%.
1 : 3 : 6-Trihydroxy-F	Orange-red "	Above 295°	4940	Orange-yellow	Blood red	C = 68.7(68.9); H = 3.5(3.4)%.
4-Methyl-6-hydroxy-F	Yellow "	135°	4935	Pale yellow	Yellow	Yellow-green	C = 76.1(76.4); H = 4.3(4.2)%.
3-Methyl-6-hydroxy-F	" "	143°	4935	" "	" "	" "	C = 76.1(76.4); H = 4.1(4.2)%.
2-Methyl-6-hydroxy-F	" "	152°	4935	" "	" "	" "	C = 76.2(76.4); H = 4.4(4.2)%.
1-Methyl-1-isopropyl- 6-hydroxy-F.	Deep yellow "	166°	4945	Bright yellow	Orange-yellow	" "	C = 77.1(77.4); H = 5.6(5.4)%.

1- <i>iso</i> -Propyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxy-F.	"	"	134°	4940	"	"	"	"	"	C=77.0(77.4); H=5.7(6.4)%.
3:4-Phenylene-6-hydroxy-F.	Orange-red	"	117°	4945	Orange-yellow	Orange-red	"	Moss-green	"	C=78.3(78.7); H=4.1(3.8)%.
2:3-Phenylene-6-hydroxy-F.	"	"	113°	4945	"	"	"	"	"	C=78.4(78.7); H=3.9(3.8)%.
2:3-(4'-Hydroxy-phenylene-6-hydroxy-F.	Brownish-red	"	163°	4960	Light brick-red	Brownish red	"	"	"	C=75.1(75.4); H=3.9(3.7)%.
3-Dimethylamido-6-hydroxy-F.	Pink	"	169°	5490	Bright pink	Pink	"	Yellow-brown	"	C=78.3(78.5); H=4.9(4.7)%.
3-Diethylamido-6-hydroxy-F.	Reddish-violet	"	163°	5500	Crimson	Reddish-violet	"	"	"	C=74.1(74.4); H=5.8(5.4)%.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
ALLAHABAD UNIVERSITY.

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